

Climate Neutrality Starts on the Ground

Unlocking Land-Based Solutions for Climate Mitigation and Resilience

Introduction

The NEVERMORE project aims to develop integrated models and tools for assessing the impacts of climate change and the efficiency of mitigation policies. Through simulations in the WILLIAM Integrated Assessment Model, two scenarios for a climate-neutral Europe by 2050, based on previous work by the Joint Research Centre (Matti et al, 2023), have been explored. The scenarios – one regulation-driven, and one market-driven – were developed using input from stakeholders, who were asked in an online survey about the feasibility and expected extent of implementing a number of policies on land use, agriculture, diet and energy in each scenario. The stakeholders engaged in the scenario development were recruited from NEVERMORE’s transnational council, technical partners and local councils. Based on the stakeholders’ aggregated inputs, the policy targets for 2050 to be used in the simulations were set. The scenario that focused more on EU regulation was deemed by the stakeholders to have greater potential for impactful policy measures. The scenario simulations included policies applied within the EU until 2050, while the rest of the world followed a business-as-usual pathway.

The results show that a substantial reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within the EU can be attained through policy measures that target agriculture, forestry, diets, transport and energy (Figure 1). However, additional and ambitious measures in all sectors would be needed to reach climate neutrality within the EU by 2050. It is also evident that global efforts are needed to curb climate change as temperature continues to rise in both scenarios (Figure 2).

Figure 1 . Both scenarios give a substantial reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from the EU countries, resulting in a 31% reduction for the market-driven scenario and a 38% reduction for the regulation-driven scenario between 2025 and 2050.

Figure 2 . The reductions in emissions from the EU countries have negligible effects on global temperature, which continues to rise.

From Farm to Climate Solution: Regenerative Agriculture Matters

Regenerative practices for both crop and livestock production would be one of the most effective means to reduce GHG emissions and sequester CO₂ within the EU through reduced use of synthetic fertilizers and improved carbon sequestration in cropland and grassland. Beyond mitigation, these measures would also enhance biodiversity and increase the EU's resilience to climate change and global instability by strengthening ecosystem services and reducing reliance on external agricultural inputs. A dietary shift toward less consumption of meat, dairy, and sugar has the potential to amplify the effect in terms of climate change mitigation and generate additional benefits such as improved public health.

Suggested actions

- Farming advisory services supported by research on regenerative practices and with national adaptations
- Lowered transition threshold through economic safeguards against productivity losses during the transition phase
- Low interest loans to farmers in transition to regenerative practices to cover investment costs
- Economic compensation for sequestered carbon as well as restored or strengthened ecosystem services

Expected impact

- Expected impact
- Substantial reduction of agricultural emissions
- Enhanced carbon sequestration in grasslands and croplands
- Increased biodiversity and strengthened ecosystem services
- Improved resilience through increased agricultural and food self-sufficiency

Relevant actors

- European Commission, Common Agricultural Policy governance bodies, Member States, national agricultural and environmental protection agencies
- Farmers, agricultural research and development, agri-food sector, civil society organizations
- Regional authorities and municipalities

More Than Trees: The act for Smarter Forestry Policy

Afforestation of disused land would be another effective measure to mitigate GHG emissions within the EU. Growing and mature forests could sequester and store large amounts of CO₂. Combined with protection of productive cropland and grassland from land use change, food security can be maintained. A transition to more sustainable forestry practices, both for current and new forests, would ensure forest productivity in balance with biodiversity and ecosystem services gains. To further support biodiversity, it is also important to strengthen and enforce protection of all remaining primary forest within the EU.

Suggested actions

- Plan and monitor land use change to avoid competition with food production
- Financial incentives and technical assistance to landowners to encourage afforestation of underutilized land and sustainable forestry methods
- Promote longer harvesting cycles, diverse species, and continuous cover forestry
- Monitor forest carbon stocks to ensure sustainable management and harvests

Expected impact

- Major net reduction of GHG emissions
- Improved forest ecosystems and biodiversity
- Strengthened ecosystem services that increase resilience against climate change impacts
- Maintained food security through protection of productive cropland and grassland

Relevant actors

- Relevant actors
- European Commission, Member States, national forestry and environmental protection agencies
- Forest- and landowners, farmers, forestry research and development
- Regional authorities and municipalities

Conclusions:

The scenario simulations in the WILLIAM model clearly show that substantial reductions of GHG emissions within the EU are possible, but that climate change will continue with negative impacts if additional and global mitigation efforts are not undertaken. The two interrelated policy pathways with a focus on agriculture and forests presented would move the EU toward climate neutrality and provide positive effects in terms of climate change adaptation, resilience and biodiversity. These policy pathways could have positive effects if applied to other regions of the world, and the EU should strive for a wider uptake of these, and other beneficial, measures through available means such as trade, international agreements and development assistance.

CATALOGUE & LOCAL TOOL

Discover the NEVERMORE Catalogue of adaptation and mitigation policies and check the Local Tool to simulate the effect of more policy scenarios

OUR WEBSITE

<https://www.nevermore-horizon.eu/>

CONSORTIUM

FOLLOW US

NEVERMORE Project

@NEVERMORE_EU

@nevermore_project_he

@nevermorehorizoneuropeproj6779

